

Impact of Online Training during COVID-19 Pandemic on Employee Performance A Case Study of NBP and HBL Bank

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Abstract:

This research investigates the Impact of online Training during COVID-19 Pandemic on Employee Performance A case study of NBP and HBL bank. Sample of 50 employees of the National Bank and 50 employees of HBL bank in Sukkur Division from several primary sources were collected. Smart PLS was used to analyse the results. For the reliability and validity of data, a structural questionnaire was created. Results Independent T-test for Training results HBL T test results 4.434 for the success of workers compared with NBP 3.11. Results show that more HBL training than NBP might have, due to the fact that the private banking sector provides its workers with more training. It was further revealed that the results Independent T-test for organizational performance Employees performance HBL T test results 5.234 compare with NBP 4.123 with male and 5.2234 for female of HBL compare with 2.784 results indicates that more organizational performance on HBL compare with NBP the results reveals that HBL is proving more growth opportunities compare with NBP.

Keywords: Online Training, COVID-19 Pandemic, Employee Performance

Introduction:

Regarding certain interest to practicing Psychiatrists are based on two reports from China about COVID-19 and patients who are already facing psychiatric illness issues. Yet as per study data, current outbreak of COVID-19 which has affected the 50 patients and 30 of the staff members has been reported in specifically Psychiatric Hospitals, and this also was the part of strict quarantine. Core reasons for this might be including overcrowding, lack of basic and much needed facilities considered as general in psychiatric hospitals, lack of basic knowledge among healthcare professionals who are working on mental health in Psychiatric Hospitals, difficult to obtain cooperation from patients of COVID-19 to strictly follow preventive measures to help in reducing spread of pandemic and to overcome the coronavirus disease, especially the patients who are also suffering from Psychotic illness. Vice Versa, those patients with already mental illness are on higher risk of relapsing or developing new episodes of further mental disorders due to the stress linked to outbreak of coronavirus disease. The purpose of every training program is to care for all the commands and exposure to the recent employee to help them make the necessary intensity of performance in their jobs rapidly and economically. Towards the existing employees, training will support and motivate them to develop capabilities to enrich their performance in their current jobs, to pursue with latest technologies or methods, and to assemble them to battle elevated and leading challenges in the future. Employee training and development projects are intended to meet distinct motives, which handout to both, employee and organization effectiveness. The factor encouraging employees to stay in their jobs is thus crucial if they are to retain employees, as it changes their efficiency. This is because professional workers testify to the productivity of companies.

There is a connection between training and employee growth and their job results, as highlighted in this literature review. The report, however, aims to check their relation on the absolute ground by considering Pakistan's banking industry as fundamental to this. In a bank, the momentous of training and development is unavoidable as they appear in the services sector. Customer services are objects that ought to be handover carefully and at the ultimate as the need and wants of customer's vitality on changing. "Training increases the distinguishing of skills among workers, whatever in turn increases the productivity and decreases frustration at jobs, which is a stance on the retention of personnel," according to Huselid (1995). Internal personnel preparation and growth minimizes the expense of selecting, retaining and internalizing individuals from the labour market. Training and growth need reciprocity, in particular when a company raises its workers' market value through training, staff is motivated to hold their jobs and take further responsibility."

The concept of training has undertaken absolute modification on the move of peripheral activity to the focus of interest in all affairs of human action. Most of in business and corporate sectors as a result of complete transformation Training has appeared as the most powerful instrument of growth and development and has keen on as well engaged everyone's attention in the organization. Education is designated by the strategic managers as the highest priority.

Bank sectors play an exceedingly key role in the nation's economy. The state bank of Pakistan is the leading public sector bank has been burdened with the additional function of releasing its obligation of social banking. Banks are onset to comprehend Human Resources as the most important area of core competence and do their finest to recruit, train, and keep the best of talents in the organizations. There is expanding cognizance that uninterrupted skill-up gradation and development is extremely vital not only for staff custody, an attribute of manpower, and both quality and quantity of output. Banks are eager to attach to the training group. As (Obisi 2001) stated "Training is a procedure through employee abilities, talent, skills, and understanding is improved and elevated. He struggles that preparation should not be needed until Scotus has discovered the need and impartial for it. "Are you confident that teaching is the foundation of sound management for making workers more successful and profitable. (Clother and Spriegel, 1977) It would be difficult for a new employee to grow and become a manager without satisfactory training and growth. Training is feasible and necessary because it enables employees to develop and prosper within the company and increase their market value, earning potential and job security, as described in (Mamoria 1995). Mamoria specifies that training promotes the mindset of workers and makes them give the company a substantial contribution. He adds that the highest economic use of materials and equipment is to be built by loyal workers. This generally held damage to a minimum.

Training and Development are the derivations of innovation and ideas that preserve organizations as opposed to future labor force turnover. When an employee's job is associated with organizational necessities and the employee is given relevant training to achieve the task, an employee's job performance, and enthusiasm to work for the organization enhances.

It recommended that the company look forward and provide their new hires with preparation and development sessions for the highest-rate reviews in the future. In the beginning of 1960, MacDonald also extended this pattern according to (Mosses 1999) and went to university of Hamburg to train its workers.

So, today, the severe organisation figure stressed the workforce 's education and growth. "Training is a systematic method of achievement and growth that improves individual, group and organisational adaptability (Goldstein and Ford 2002). Development refers to the achievement that dominates the learning of new skills for employee growth.

In the context of Pakistan, the economy of the country is facing a crisis due to various reasons; people do not have enough capital to invest. Due to this reason, people strive to approach to the best organization, which provide them up to the mark service on the effective rates. This means that banks employee need to continue training according to the need of their jobs. The proposed study will investigate the impact of Training and development on employee performance, which will enable the banks to adopt essential strategies for successful Training implementation.

Literature Review

According to the dictionary training meaning given below: Training means exercise, efforts, and activity. It was important for the company to coordinate training very attentively (Michael, armstray, 2000); Professor Dr. Abdul Ghafoor Awan & Farwa Saeed in 2014 reported, that training enhanced employee efficiency. Training refers to the exact growth and development of human beings on this planet. Results show that preparation is an efficient and reliable method for the performance of employees. In order to create a partnership between staff education and employee results, the training protocol for staff in TA must be established (Miss Bushra Muzaffar 2014). It is shown that preparation is an critical element to affect the success of employees. (Ahmed Mohamed Mohamud 2014) noted that training affects public sector organizations' employee efficiency. 100 workers in the Machakos branch have collected data. Findings indicate that training has a substantial effect on the performance of the workforce and benefits the individual staff as well as the corporation.

(Ngugi Martha Nyakeo Nyokabi 2014) stressed that training is an integral part of enhancing the capacity for successful performance of new and current employees. Research demonstrates that employee training is also both a required factor in the company and workers; it enhances job efficiency, motivates employees and increases employee morale. Employees should learn and learn to help them in their performance enhancement or advancement.

In this changing climate, training is very important (Ekta Srivastava & Dr Nisha Agarwal 2014). In potential preparation, it should be available to clarify to banks and workers so that it helps. The training sketch should comply with employees' requirements (Ginsberg, 1997). In order to produce better results (Partlow 1996; Tihanyi et al , 2000), an company must establish successful and efficiently training in accordance with the employee requirement. It appears that training and development plays an essential role in the performances of both employees and organization while, a poor quality training sketch is nothing as well as the wastage of time and assets, (Tsaur and lin, 2004). As stated by (B.Janakiram, 2010) training is the acquisition of ideas or abstraction, hypothesis, skills, knowledge and other attributes to the job appoint, to expand the level of general organizational effectiveness. In developing countries, like Pakistan, there is an extensive need for abundantly trained faculty at entire levels and entire positions in all organizations. Afterward, in the process of economic growth and development, Banks are effective partners. Training, thence, has to be an on-going process ever. Training is projected and analytical adoption of action through attainment phase, programs, and exercise which conclusion in the attendant accomplish the levels of competencies, abilities, awareness, aptitude, and talent to execute the task adequately. Identify with above, (Beardwell et al 2004), claimed that organisational and technical innovations constantly affect the knowledge of few employers of the requirement of a distinctive and continuous commitment in the training and development phase to achieve the achievements based upon their employees' abilities and skills. Education, as indicated by (Zohair Abbas, 2014) is an important factor for an employee 's growth since few employees have a lack of education, experience and expertise in order to perform successful tasks in due course. Organization reduces their productivity and growth due to ineffectiveness of training and development of employees, (Franklin Dang Kum, 2014).

(Ginthiji Angela, 2014) emphasised that training both affects the efficiency of the employees and enhances their employees' commitment to the process of change. Customer training is needed to cope with the challenge burden that banks regularly face, as reported by (Dr Muhammad Ghaffari Fard, 2015).

(Cynthia Owusu Boateng, 2011) stressed that training has a real or positive impact on employee productivity on the output of employees. Training accommodates advantage to employee performance and organized by enhancement of skills, knowledge, abilities, and behaviors. (Benedicta Appiah, 2010) pointed out that training improves the employee's knowledge, skills, attribute, and eventually their performance and capacity in the organization. (Atolar Janepher Adongo, 2013) pointed out that the organisation which ignores the significance of training leads to an excessive turnover and also increased the costs of engaging new employees and ultimately, restricted the profitability of the organization (Mahbuba Sultana, 2013). (Ngugi Martha, Nyakeo Nyokaboi, 2014) emphasised that preparation plays a critical role in improving the competences for successful success for both new and current employees. (Pangorso, Mulyaningsih, and Saraswati, 2014) pointed out that the motive of training is to inspire employees to achieve the target of the organization. Training becomes a need in this improving environment. As stated by (Chew, 2014) training improves employee's special skills and improves employee's abilities that the organization will demand in the future.

(Barringer, 2005) highlighted for the rapid growth of the organization, the firm has to provide training to staff to achieve their objectives. The short-term training phase to improve and reinforce the talents , skills, and other qualities of employees (Steinmetz, Lawrence 1996). Growth, on the other hand, is a long-term phase to develop the employee's theoretical, intellectual knowledge and skills. (Nadler and Nadler 1991) noted that the elements in the human resource development (HRD) model include training and development. (Armstrong, 2009) has diversified training from development by stated his concept in the statement that development refers to adopt new skills and knowledge that helps to improve performance in the future job while training refers to motivate employees to better perform in their current job. (Gerbohm, 2000) employee development project contains a collection of learning techniques and inspiring learning environments that assure employees to elevate their skills and other attributes applicable to their job. (Srimannaryana M.2011) highlighted that training, development is an essential component in the

advance Human Resource Management, and the area of training and development differ from one to another. The current research is depending on primary data. The research discloses that performance betterment invented because of training is an intensely admired measured.

(Ramakrishna et al. 2012) highlighted that the Human Resource Development department should execute a more aggressive aspect to assemble the employees to accept the challenges. The banks don't mean to have a focus on particular plans, policies, and discover strategies, banks must have to display appropriateness and effectiveness incomplete those strategies.

(Nagar 2009) highlighted that the efficiency of training projects must be organized by commercial banks in public along in the private sector.

(Thomas N. Garavab 1997) pointed out that an employee cannot perform effectively their task without any training.

(Partlow, 1996; Tihanji et al. 2000) highlighted that trained employees achieve their tasks efficiently as to untrained employees.

A organisation has an essential need to develop training programmes for its workers to help fulfil the company's objectives as a whole (Flynn et al, 1995; Kaynak 2003). Training and development enhance the comprehensive performance of the organization (Shepard, Jon, et al, 2003).

(Lynton and Pareek) highlighted training as a whole that contains generally of well-classified opportunities for employees to obtain essential responsiveness and skills.

As stated by (Sari, 2009) training and development seem like one of the initial processes of Human Resource Management and it refers to the curriculum compose to teach the staff concerning the firm essentials, civilize them on the comprehensive rules of an organization, to facilitate them with technical knowledge, which is necessary to fulfill job tasks effectively.

As stated by (Cole, 2002) training is a learning activity that is sponsored towards the acquiring of particular knowledge and skills for the task.

Similarly, (Abbas, 2014) training enhance and improves the capabilities of the employee as well as sharpens their thinking capability and creativity to make better decisions in time. Additionally, delegate employees to manage the customers compulsorily and act to their arguments in encouraging way (Hollenbeck, Derue & Guzzo, 2004). Moreover, training establishes self-efficacy and conclusions in weak practices efficiently and effectively. Simultaneously, it is not easy for an employee to perform well without any pre-training (Garavan 1997). Technical and professional skills are essential for the employee; therefore, provide training opportunities to an employee that they can perform well (Kraieger, 2002, Barber, 2004)

Moreover, employee training and development programs are necessary for all organization to stay connected and competitive in the market place (Fenn, 2000)

On other hand, (Logan, 2000; Rosenwald, 2000) has assured and accepted their relationship of employee training and development and employee performance therefore, companies have to provide effective training and development programs to employees for getting success.

Data Collection Methodology

Sample of 50 employees of the National Bank and 50 employees of HBL bank in Sukkur Division from several primary sources were collected. Smart PLS was used to analyse the results. For the reliability and validity of data, a structural questionnaire was created.

Independent T-test for Training impact on Employees performance during COVID-19

Training					
NBP					
	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	T test
Training	Male	78	3.2758	.8972	3.11
	Female	22	3.234	.86.667	
HBL					
Training	Male	80	4.456	.9374	4.434
	Female	20	4.123	.8845	3.13

According to the results Independent T-test for Training impact on Employees performance HBL T test results 4.434 compare with NBP 3.11, results indicates that more impact of Training on HBL compare with NBP, may be because of private banking sector is more trainings provided to their employees.

Independent T-test for Organizational Performance during COVID-19

Organizational Performance					
NBP					
	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	T test
Organizational Performance	Male	80	4.124	.8694	4.123
	Female	20	4.023	.7843	2.784
HBL					
Organizational Performance	Male	70	4.903	.91232	5.234
	Female	30	4.789	.8808	5.22

According to the results Independent T-test for organizational performance Employees performance HBL T test results 5.234 compare with NBP 4.123 with male and 5.2234 for female of HBL compare with 2.784 results indicates that more organizational performance on HBL compare with NBP the results reveals that HBL is proving more growth opportunities compare with NBP.

Conclusions: The current research explore the online training on the employee performance during COVID-19 pandemics. Most of the employees from both banks were not happy about online training because of language and other barriers and internet issue. According to the results Independent T-test for Job satisfaction NBP T test results 3.22 compare with HBL 2.87 with male and 3.11 for female of NBP compare with 2.11 results indicates that Job satisfaction among on NBP compare with HBL. The results indicates that NBP employees are more satisfied in term of Job security and more satisfy compare with HBL.

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